

Gas bubble venting: A novel behavioral indicator of stress in juvenile Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*)

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Abstract

Reliable, non-invasive behavioral indicators of stress are essential for improving real-time welfare monitoring in aquaculture, yet few validated markers are currently available for assessing the welfare of farmed fish. This study aimed to identify novel stress-related behaviors in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*). To this end, dominant–subordinate relationships were induced through repeated dyadic interactions between size-matched pairs of territorial juvenile fish over four days, followed by an overnight interaction (n = 10 pairs), with 12 fish kept in isolation as controls. Behavioral observations were focused on traits with potential for automated detection and revealed a distinct multi-trait behavioral syndrome in socially subordinate individuals: reduced feed intake (p = 0.04), higher vertical positioning in the water column (p < 0.001), and more frequent release of gas bubbles from the swim bladder (p = 0.02). Among these traits, bubble release emerged as a novel, conspicuous and sensitive indicator of acute stress. Frequency of bubble release correlated positively with the number of aggressive acts received from dominant fish (p = 0.018), though not with plasma cortisol levels (p = 0.10). Nonetheless, cortisol was significantly elevated in subordinate fish compared to controls (p = 0.003) but not compared to dominant fish (p = 0.14). This observation suggests that bubble release may serve as a more sensitive marker of acute social stress than physiological stress responses such as cortisol. Given the conspicuous nature and clear visual signature of bubble release, follow-up studies should explore the potential for automated detection using computer vision or bioacoustic methods. Such monitoring could enable earlier identification of stressed individuals in fish farming, supporting more proactive and individualized welfare assessments. Vertical positioning was also influenced by social status and may represent an additional visually accessible trait linked to stress, although further research is needed to assess its general applicability. In summary, this study suggests potential extensions to the current repertoire of non-invasive welfare indicators for farmed fish and provides a foundation for continued research into behavioral welfare monitoring in Atlantic salmon.